

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER BUYING ATTITUDE OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO LAKME IN PALAKKAD CITY

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Abstract: Reference to Lakme in Palakkad City” examines the buying behavior and preferences of study titled “A Study on Customer Buying Attitude of Cosmetic Products with Special consumers This towards Lakme cosmetic products. The main objective of the study is to understand factors influencing customer purchase decisions, satisfaction level, and brand preference. Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire from selected respondents in Palakkad City. Statistical tools such as Percentage Analysis, Chi-Square Test, and ANOVA were used for data analysis. The study analyses demographic factors like age, income, education, and their impact on buying attitude. Findings reveal that quality, brand image, price, and availability significantly influence customer purchasing decisions. The study concludes with suggestions to improve customer satisfaction and strengthen brand loyalty towards Lakme products.

Keywords: Consumer Awareness, Brand Responsibility, Ethical Consumerism, Sustainable cosmetic.

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer satisfaction has been subjects of the great interest to the organizations and researcher like. The prime objective of organizations is to maximize profits and to minimize cost. Profit maximization can be obtained through increase in sales with lesser costs. Profit maximization can be obtained through increase in sales with lesser costs. One of the important factors that can help to increase sales is customer satisfaction, because satisfaction leads to customer loyalty, recommendations and repeat purchasing. A customer is an individual or business that purchases the goods or services produced by a business. Attracting customer is the primary goal of the businesses, because it is the customer who creates for goods and services. Lakme is an Indian cosmetics brand which is owned by Hindustan Unilever. Having Kareena Kapoor and chamma as the ambassador, it ranked at number 1 among the cosmetics brands in India. Lakme started as a 100% subsidiary of Tata Oil Mills (Tomco). It was named after the French opera Lakme which itself is the French form of Devi Lakshmi (the Hindu goddess of wealth) who is renowned for her beauty. It was started in 1952 famously, because then Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru was concerned that Indian women were spending precious foreign exchange on beauty products and personally requested JRD Tata to manufacture them in India. Simone Tata joined the company as director and went on to become the chairperson. In 1996, Tata sold off their stakes in Lakme Lever to HUL, for Rs 200 Core.

2. OBJECTIVES

1. To know the customer perception towards usage of Lakme products.
2. To find out the factor which influence the customer buying behavior.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Lakme products are helpful in creating awareness and perception among customers.
2. Advertisements develop self-concepts in order to induce purchase decisions.

3 Lakme is an admired beauty brand and a leader in the beauty industry.

4. With and in depth understanding of international cosmetic technology and beauty and skincare needs of Indian women. Lakme offers an all-round beauty experience through its products and services at Lakme salons.

MISSION

An Ally to The Classic Indian Woman, Lakme Inspires Her to Express the Unique Beauty And Sensuality Within Enabling Her to Realize the Potency of Her Beauty.

DATA COLLECTION

The source of data includes primary and secondary data sources.

PRIMARY DATA

A primary data is a data which is collected for first time for the particular interest to collect more information. In this study, the primary data was collected using questionnaire.

SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data consist of information that already exists somewhere, having been collected for some other purpose. In this study, the secondary data was collected from studies, magazines, journals and websites.

SAMPLE DESIGN

Convenience sampling method was used for collecting respondents, in the method of sampling, sample were selected on the convenience of both researcher and respondents.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size selected for this study is 123 respondents.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY

The collected data were analyses and interpreted properly to find the results of the research work. Conventional tools like descriptive tables and percentage were used for the purpose of analysis. The graph and charts have also been made use of where ever necessary. Further, the following specific tools were used,

CHI-SQUARE

A chi-square test is a statistical test used to compare observed results with expected results.

The purpose of this test is to determine if a difference between observed data and expected data is due to chance, or if it is due to a relationship between the variables you are studying

REGRESSION:

Regression analysis is a set of statistical methods used for the estimation of relationships between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It can be utilized to assess the strength of the relationship between variables and for modelling the future relationship between them

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted for the period of three months. The primary data was collected and it took one-month time period. The review of literature and discussions with the field experts in the species board took another one month. Data analysis and interpretation was carried for a period of one month and final period of the report took the remaining period.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS * REASON FOR PURCHASE BY THERESPONDENTS

NULL HYPOTHESIS: There is no significant relationship between the Age of therespondents and Reason for purchase by the respondents

ALTERNATE HYPOTHESIS: There is significant relationship between the Age of the respondents and Reason for purchase by the respondents

Age * Reason for purchase Cross tabulation

Count

		Reason for purchase				Total
		price	variety	quality	Availability	
age	15-20	0	0	10	0	10
	21-25	0	0	68	0	68
	26-30	5	10	11	1	27
	31-35	0	0	0	30	30
Total		5	10	89	31	135

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	195.919 ^a	9	.000
Likelihood Ratio	187.318	9	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	23.775	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	135		

.8 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .37.

- there is a significant relationship between the age of the respondents and Reason for purchase by the respondents

5. CONCLUSION

Today, the world cosmetic industry faces a huge demand and challenges in providing assured quality of cosmetic products. With the advancement in technology, globalization and increased purchasing power, the consumers in recent years have become more aware of hygiene and beauty, which is the foremost reason behind the rapid development of cosmetic industry. The female behavior is complex and dynamic as the aspirations of every female community are to look beautiful and attractive. The cosmetic is considered as a powerful weapon which the women feel would transform their normal looks to an attractive and a presentable one. It is believed that beauty products promote a sense of emotional wellbeing of the women. The cosmetic products in the present era have moved from luxury category to most essential category. Hence, the marketers of cosmetic products have to be vigilant and should be able to realise the needs of the presentday cosmetic users. They should be thoroughly studied about their behavior towards the purchase and use of cosmetics. The different factors such as quality, ingredients and safety of cosmetic products found influencing the buying decision of cosmetic consumers

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